

Kusman Subaraja ^{*1}, Ary Setijadi Prihatmanto ^{*2}, Agus Sukoco ^{*3}, Dr. Rahadian Yusuf ^{*4}, Vitradisa Pratama ⁵,
Dr. Agus Budiyo ^{*6}, Dr. Reza Darmakusuma ^{*7}

^{1,2,4,6,7*} *Bandung Institute of Technology,*

^{3*} *Universitas bandar Lampung,* ^{4*} *universitas Mayasari Bakti*

Abstract: Outdoor classroom learning is important to be carried out to provide a real learning experience, train environment concern, creativity, social skills and ability to manage information resources. Outdoor classroom learning is a learning activity utilising the environment as a learning medium. The obstacle of outdoor classroom learning consist of students' focus are easily get distracted, lack of students' supervision, unidentified learning location causes the students prone to disorientation, evaluation of learning activities takes a lot of time. The YukMaCa system is built on Augmented Reality technology and Location Base Service on Android platform and a website portal which is developed with the aim to overcome the problems of outdoor classroom learning. The system works by combining virtual objects and the real world through mobile devices, virtual objects will appear in certain locations and deliver information or evaluation interactively, system is equipped with route directions and supervision of user's location. The result of testing on ease's level for YukMaCa mobile is 6.25 and 6.52 for YukMaCa website, usability score from student respondents is 74.67 and 78.17 from teacher. The average overall testing of YukMaCa system ease level is 6.39 (easy to use) and overall the average of YukMaCa system usability score is 76.42 (Acceptable), *therefore the yukmaca system can be used for outdoor classroom learning*

Keywords: *ICT, Digital Media, games, field trip learning, outdoor classroom learning, Augmented Reality, Location Based Services (LBS)*

1. Introduction

Outdoor classroom learning being an important thing because it provides a real and direct learning experience of the object being studied, triggers critical thinking, creativity, practice the communication, cooperation, the environment concern, and train the skills for life, furthermore it is able to hone a skills in searching and processing the information sources in line with developing the education toward a creative Indonesia in 2045 [1] [2]. Outdoor classroom learning utilises the environment as a learning medium, including the natural environment, the social environment aiming to introduce the order of life in the community or artificial environment such as industrial zones or circles of human engineering [3]. To support the achievement of learning and academic abilities of students toward outdoor classroom learning which are carried out with a particular learning model (eg contextual, cooperative learning models, inquiry learning models) [4]. There are a number of obstacles in outdoor classroom learning, namely, students' focus are easily get distracted, lack of students' supervision, period of implementation take a long time for unidentified learning location causes the students prone to disorientation, evaluation of learning activities takes a lot of time because they have to direct and condition students along with supervising in a wide area, a wide area is prone to make students' experience disorientation and not all the places have clear direction and accessible and not all places can be identified from the online map system, the evaluation of outdoor classroom learning activities is generally done manually so that the teacher has to provide enough time, the selection of outdoor classroom learning will depend on material content delivered so that the learning location is not always the same.

Given the importance outdoor classroom learning, there must be a solution to the obstacles of outdoor classroom learning development, and that is the based of this research. Each

student in general has a device that can detect their position information in the form of a mobile device, so that information can be used to monitor the location of students [5][6], location information coupled with digital media systems can be built into an attractive and interactive system that be used to help outdoor classroom learning in order to get students' attention that can be directed to the expected learning content, due to the media is a means to channel information, with the result that an interesting media can convey information better [7] [8] [9].

By utilizing location information, in terms of introducing the environment, it can be helped by providing directions and routes in an actual and interactive way. Therefore, to overcome the problem of outdoor classroom learning system, it must be able to accommodate the delivery of information through digital media interactively, utilizing location-based information management, such the Augmented Reality (AR) technology and Location Base Service (LBS) are selected in developing systems for outdoor classroom learning. To facilitate content management, evaluation and management of values, a website portal-based information system is chosen, considering that the system must be easily accessible. Based on the explanation that has been submitted, it is obtained the formulation of the problem, how to build a system for outdoor classroom learning by using Augmented Reality (AR) technology, Location Base Service (LBS) and website portal-based information systems. The purpose of the system is to overcome problems in outdoor classroom learning, in order to students can get the desired learning experience. In the implementation stage, students are directed to search for various information directly, expected to be able to independently manage information sources with the concept of literacy, hence the system developed is named the YukMaCa system (Yuk Mari Cari).

2. Theory

1. Augmented Reality Technology

Augmented comes from the word augment, which means adding or improving something. In Augmented Reality (AR), graphics, sound, and touch feedback are added to the real world to create a better user experience. Currently there are several types of augmented reality:[10],

1. Marker Based Augmented Reality,
It is an augmented reality based marker (Image Recognition) using a camera and several types of visual markers (QR / 2D codes or images)
2. Markerless Augmented Reality,
It also referred as location-based, position-based, or GPS augmented reality.
3. Projection Based Augmented Reality,
The main working mechanism is by projecting artificial light into the real world. Through the projected light it allows the interaction with humans in the form of touch.
4. Superimposition Based Augmented Reality
In this type of augmented reality either partially or completely replace the original view of an object with a new and enlarged view of the same object.

Augmented reality can be used on several devices that are distinguished by the type of device including, on a smart phone and tablet device, or a computer system that is equipped with a screen and camera [11].

There are some advantages and disadvantages of augmented reality, such as providing new experiences to mobile users, helping in providing visual warnings and reminders, and proving to be an effective tool in gestural communication, meanwhile the disadvantages of augmented reality is it needs high specification device [11].

One of the uses of augmented reality is in the field of education, augmented reality will stimulate the curiosity of the learning participants then will help to create the dialogue to understand more about what is learned, multimedia content such as text, sound, images and videos, digital objects, are examples of learning media that allows to be used in augmented reality [11].

In the field of education, augmented reality has been widely used, this can be seen from a review of 30 research journals on augmented reality applications in education by Jorge Bacca et al. the results show that the augmented reality application is dominated by science learning, which is 40.6% and the most widely used for the bachelor level is 34.38%, high school level 12.50%, junior high school level and elementary school respectively. 43.75% of augmented reality applications were used to explain learning topics, as much as 40.6% for enrichment and 18.75% for educational games, augmented reality in education gave positive results including 53.13 % shows improvement in learning performance, 28.13% improves learning motivation, comfort and better attitude in learning, from the type of augmented reality technology used as much as 59.38% in marker based, 12.5% using makerless augmented reality and 21.88 % uses location based augmented reality [12].

2. Location Based Services (LBS)

Location Based Services (LBS) are information services that can be accessed by mobile devices through a network then they have the ability to know the location of the device [13].

As shown in Fig 1, an explanation of LBS can be described as a service that is at the intersection of three technologies, namely the geographic information system (GIS), Internet services, and mobile devices. GIS is a service system that has ability to build, store, manage and display information with geographic references with one of its products being a map.

Fig 1 LBS technology[13]

LBS or location-based service which is a service that reacts actively to changes in position entities then they are to detect the location of objects and provide services in accordance with the known location of the object. In using location based services there are several components needed, as illustrated in Figure 2 [13] :

1. mobile device is used to request information needed,
2. communication network, as a network link service or information will ask a request network to the provider server,
3. positioning network, it will be used for services processing
4. Service and application provider, responsible for processing information services requested by the users.
5. data and content provider, it is in form of service provider information that can be requested by the users,

Figure 2 Basic components of LBS: Users, Communication Networks, Positioning, Service Providers, and Content Providers [13].

3. Text to Speech

Text to speech (TTS) uses to help those who have difficulty in reading. TTS works by converting the text into sound, the sound of the TTS is the result of a computer, usually the speed of the resulting sound can be slowed down and accelerated then the available sound varies come up. [14]

TTS helps the users who have problems in language. It helps in conveying the information through audio media or help users who have different learning styles. [2]

4. Haversine formula

This equation can be used to determine the distance between two points on the ball given longitude and latitude, the calculation of this equation is quite accurate in which this equation ignores the height and depth on the surface of the earth [15], so it can be used to determine the distance between two points based on geographical coordinate system (longitude and latitude).

Mathematically the *haversine* equation is written as follows:

$$d = 2r \arcsin \left(\sqrt{\sin^2 \left(\frac{\text{lat}_2 - \text{lat}_1}{2} \right) + \cos(\text{lat}_1) \cdot \cos(\text{lat}_2) \cdot \sin^2 \left(\frac{\text{long}_2 - \text{long}_1}{2} \right)} \right) \dots\dots(1) [15]$$

Where r is the radius constant of the earth which is 6371 km, lat2 and long2 (destination coordinates), lat1 and long1 (origin coordinates).

3. Methods

Augmented reality technology is used as a medium for conveying information in the form of avatars and questions, questions and avatars are conditioned to appear at certain coordinates by utilizing location base service technology, the aims are to direct students to be active, obtain information contextually according to the object being studied, technology a location base service is also used to monitor the user's position and provide instruction to find the directions.

With the aim of increasing students' interest in learning activities that is given the game elements in the form of avatar search which the avatar can only be taken by one person, and by taking avatars increasing the student scores, students can also get a score from answering the questions correctly. To help facilitate the management and placement of system content, it equipped with a website portal, which through the portal the teacher can make account settings, score recording, management and placement of questions, avatars and locations. Management of system content can also be done through a mobile application that will accommodate the teacher to finds a point that is suitable for spontaneously placing an avatar, problem, or location with more accurate coordinates, or to make improvements to the content directly in the location. By facilitating the data to be accessed widely, a server is required to be in the YukMaCa system. The relationship between mobile devices, servers and website portals can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Relation diagram between mobile devices, servers and website portals

The YukMaCa system is designed by consisting from a mobile application and website portal, in order to obtain the expected results that the mobile application created must be able to meet the following elements:

1. It is equipped with login and register form, (Spk-1).
2. It access functions for logout, route, and user position information (Spk-2).
3. There is a route recommendation, user position information and about (Spk-3).
4. It is able to present information about account, score, number of question and avatar (Spk-4).

5. The questions and avatars appear according to placement points, notifications for questions and avatars, increase 10 point for grab avatar and correct answer of question, avatars for deliver information, avatars that have been grab by one user can not be found by other users (Spk-5).
6. Having the function for managing avatar (Add, edit and delete) for content and placement of avatar (for admin users) (Spk-6).
7. Having the function for managing question (Add, edit and delete) for the content and placement of placement points (for admin users) (Spk-7).
8. Having the function for managing place (Add, edit and delete) for content and placement of location placement points (for admin users) (Spk-8).
9. Having the function to managing user login permissions (Spk-9).

Whereas for YukMaCa based website portals, it must fulfil the following elements:

1. The start page of the portal can present the user's position through the marker, search for the user's position, view the user details (name of the user account, email, and score) (Spk-10).
2. It is equipped with login page, and function setting YukMaCa mobile user login permissions (Spk-11).
3. The portal can present the user's position, search for the user's position, view user details (name of user account, email, and score) (Spk-12).
4. The portal can present the position of the question through the marker, search for the position of the question, see the details of the question (the problem editor, the answer to the question, the answer key) (Spk-13).
5. Portal can present avatar position through marker, search avatar position, see avatar details (avatar name and information on avatar) (Spk-14).
6. The portal can present the destination position through the marker, search for the position of the avatar, see location details (destination name and information on the location) (Spk-15).
7. The portal can present the user's markers, questions, avatars, goals and details of each content simultaneously (Spk-16).
8. Having the function of viewing, adding, editing and deleting user data (Spk-17).
9. Having the function of viewing, adding, editing and deleting avatar data (Spk-18).
10. Having the function of viewing, adding, editing and deleting problem data (Spk-19).
11. Having the function of viewing, adding, editing and deleting location data (Spk-20).
12. Having the function of managing the recap or report for user data, avatars, questions, and location and recap data can be downloaded in table processing format (Spk-21).
13. Having the password change status page(Spk-22).
14. Having a page and logout function to be displayed (Spk-23).

Based on the elements that must be fulfilled, the YukMaCa system architecture is designed, Figure 4 shows how the YukMaCa system's architecture.

Figure 4 YukMaCa System Architecture

The Interface Layer, on this layer there are three modules, namely the acquisition data that is responsible for retrieving data, the display user interface displays information and augmented objects (avatars or questions) on the user's screen and event capture to handle these features. *The Control Layer*, on this layer there are two modules, namely data processing and event control, this layer has the task to manage the data whether it will be accepted or rejected, and interpret what is given by the user then presented to the user according to the results of the process. *The Service Layer*, this layer is responsible for ensuring all services are running properly so that the features and functions of the YukMaCa system work properly. To present information from the avatar to the user will be done through voice media and to reduce the burden of application information will be stored in the form of text in the data base, then *text to speech service* is needed in handling the function, the avatar or problem is designed to appear on the user's screen if the difference between device locations with the location of the question or avatar less than 15 meters, the difference is obtained from the haversine equation, *user account identification* to ensure the type of account, then the data buffer is responsible for handling temporary data storage and dealing directly with the data base, *navigation and position service* tasked with providing services route recommendations and position information to users dynamically, navigation and position service are the result of interpretation of input from LBS users and service providers so that, information is expected, the engine vuforia is used to provide the appearance of mobile applications like an augmented reality application. *Infrastructure Service*, this layer is responsible for accessing information either to the data base or LBS service providers that provide route information

and digital maps or 3D avatar objects, to be processed and presented to the users.

4. Results

Many types of mobile platforms can be selected, so then the YukMaCa mobile system can work as expected, that platform must be following some features:

- Supporting for dynamically displaying digital maps along with route instructions,
- Supporting for running augmented reality tools (vuforia engine),
- Accessing position information via the gps system,
- Supporting the system that can convert text into sound.

Based on the features needed, the platform to develop YukMaCa mobile is the Android platform, the reasons are because:

- Android has full support and is integrated with Google Maps which can dynamically provide destination route information and position location information on digital maps [16],
- Augmented reality tools like the vuforia engine can only run and function properly on the android platform [17] [18],
- Android devices are integrated with GPS and the Android system has access to retrieve location information from GPS devices [16],
- Android has support in converting text into voice or voice to text both online and offline [16].

Android has other advantages, for instances as an operating system that is widely used by users of mobile smart devices [19] [20].

The mobile app is used by students as then users and the website portal is used by the teacher as a user. Students are required to have an account to be able to use YukMaCa

android, in which the account can be registered by the student independently or by the teacher, then on the initial page YukMaCa android will provide the facility to login or register, as shown in Figure 4 (a), When the user is successful login, the user enters the main part of the android YukMaCa application.

Figure 4 (a) Login and register pages, (b) Pages that display menus and information boards, (c) Display route recommendations and position monitors, (d) Augmented objects (questions), (e) Augmented objects (avatars), (f) Setting the question, (g) Setting the avatar, (h) Setting the location

Figure 4 (b) shows the main part, in this section, the user can see the information about the name of the account used, scores, number of avatars existed, the number of questions and questions answered. YukMaCa Android uses the vuforia SDK as a tool to display what the rear camera captures on the main screen.

Access to student user's menu is restricted as shown in Figure 4 (b) for the logout menu, monitor map as a tool to monitor the position and search for route guides, and the menu about. Figure 4 (c) shows how to monitor user position and route recommendations, the destination location can be selected in the column next to the map, the list of locations appearing is in accordance with the location marking done by the admin or

teacher. In raising the avatar and questions can be seen in Figure 4 (d) and (e). If the user enters login as admin, he will gain access and can set the problem, avatar and location as shown in Figure 4 (f) for setting the problem, picture 4 (g) for setting the avatar and figure 4 (h) for setting the location.

In the YukMaCa portal website application that is used by the teacher or admin aiming for managing the content for security reasons, then to arrange it, there must be an account registered as an admin, but if you do not have a user admin account, the user can open the YukMaCa website, however will be limited to seeing the user's position and information in form of the marker.

Figure 5 User markers (yellow), questions (blue), avatars (green) and location (orange)

To be able to make settings as an admin, the user must login as admin. On the admin home page, you can see the position for each user location, avatar, problem and location, each of which is represented by a yellow marker for the user, blue for the problem, green for the avatar, and orange for the location, the marker displayed can be set to appear one by one based on the category or simultaneously depending on the check box that is activated on the map. Figure 5 shows an image of the admin main page.

Figure 6 Recap the question data page

To see the recap of user account data, questions, avatars and locations, it is shown in the form of tables that are loaded in different pages based on their categories as shown in Figure 6 to recap the question data. To add a new question and determine the coordinates where the question is placed, a map is provided so that the user just points at one of the points on the map and in the coordinate column lift coordinates appear, as well as to add locations and avatars.

Figure 7 Page for adding new questions

5. Testing and Analysis

System testing was carried out for 30 students as users respondents and 30 teachers as admin, the number of samples considered that respondents for research were at least 20 respondents [21], testing included level ease of use of the system through a post task questionnaire where respondents were asked to carry out the tasks as stated in the questionnaire, then based on the experience of the respondent will give a response about the ease of using the system which is stated in seven scales is very difficult, difficult, quite difficult, enough, quite easy, easy and very easy which are given weight 1,2,3,4,5 , 6, and 7. Table 1 and table 2 the task code and the specification reference.

Tabel 1 Student task

No	Task	Reference Specifications
1	F1	Spk-1
2	F2	Spk-2
3	F3	Spk-3
4	F4	Spk-4
5	F5	Spk-5

Tabel 2 Teacher task

No	Task	Reference Specifications
1	F1	Spk-6
2	F2	Spk-7
3	F3	Spk-8
4	F4	Spk-9

The tasks given refer to the system specifications, so that by testing the level of ease of use indirectly the respondent also tested the system work function, the recapitulation of the test results is in Figure 8 for the teacher and student respondents

Figure 8 Results of testing the level of ease of Android YukMaCa

For F1 to F4 task from student respondents obtained on a scale 6, which means that the parts are easy to use, but on F5 obtained on a scale 5, which means quite easy, this is because the F5 task is to look for questions and avatars, but not all respondents directly find an avatar or questions easily. Whereas, for testing the ease level from teacher respondents for assignments F1 to F4 all get a scale above 6, which means managing the content of the YukMaCa system using an android is easy to be used.

Whereas for testing the ease of the teacher respondents for assignments F1 to F4 all get a scale above 6 which means managing the content of the YukMaCa system using an easy-to-use android application by the teacher. Whereas for the YukMaCa portal testing to find out the ease of use carried out by only the teacher considering that the YukMaCa website portal function is dominant to the administration or content management function, the results obtained are in Figure 9,

Figure 9 Results of testing the level ease of YukMaCa portal

For all tasks except for F11, get a minimum score of 6, which means that the tasks can be done well and are easy to

with the assignment referring to the system specification reference as shown in table 3

Tabel 3 The task is to test the ease of the YukMaCa portal

No	Task	reference specifications
1	F1	Spk-10
2	F2	Spk-11
3	F3	Spk-12
4	F4	Spk-13
5	F5	Spk-14
6	F6	Spk-15
7	F7	Spk-16
8	F8	Spk-17
9	F9	Spk-18
10	F10	Spk-18
11	F11	Spk-20
12	F12	Spk-21
13	F13	Spk-22
14	F14	Spk-23

implement, thus reflecting that the website portal functions according to the specifications in the design because the assignments are made based on system specifications, but for F11 assignments some respondents experiencing difficulties in raising avatar choices on managing avatars because of poor internet connection so that it gives a fairly easy score.

Meanwhile to find out the usefulness of the YukMaCa android application, usability testing was done using SUS (Usability Scale Software) with students as respondents and the YukMaCa portal by the teacher as respondents in order to see the overall system usage, usability testing was done by giving a 5-scale questionnaire (Strongly Agree, Agree, Doubt, Disagree, Strongly Disagree) to the respondent, with a questionnaire consisting of 10 odd statement statements with positive words and even statements with negative tone, with weight for positive statements 4,3,2,1,0 and weight for negative statements 0,1,2,3,4. The value scale given by the respondent will be multiplied by 2.5 for each statement so that the final value will be in the range of 100 for each respondent.

The statement given is about the ease of using the YukMaCa system, system features and the usefulness of the YukMaCa system for learning outside the classroom. Table 4 shows the statements for student and for teacher respondents.

Table 4 Usability testing instruments

No	Teacher	Student
1	The marker displayed on the YukMaCa portal helps facilitate monitoring of the user's position, avatar, questions and location as well as the information displayed on the avatar's details is enough	YukMaCa Android is easy to operate
2	The YukMaCa portal makes it difficult to organize content and map location points, avatars and questions	I feel unhappy and uncomfortable when using YukMaCa android
3	The YukMaCa portal helps make it easier to recap scores or YukMaCa user scores	I want to recommend other people to use YukMaCa
4	I do not want to recommend others to use the YukMaCa system for outdoor based learning	The avatar that appeared was uninteresting, so I was not interested in listening to information from the avatar
5	The YukMaCa portal makes it easy to manage user accounts, (create, update and delete)	The YukMaCa Android application helps me get to know the environment I visit
6	The YukMaCa system is less suitable when applied to outdoor based learning	I do not agree if YukMaCa is used in outdoor based learning such as tourism or industrial visits
7	I am interested in trying the YukMaCa system in on my class	The question feature helps direct me to pay attention to and observe certain environments or objects
8	Setting function (create, change and delete) for questions, avatars and locations on Android YukMaCa is not needed because it is annoying and unuseful	I feel that I don't challenged, curious or even happy to look for more avatars and questions even though it can add to the score I get
9	Feature questions and avatars on the YukMaCa system can help direct the focus and attention of users to certain objects or environments to increase students' active participation in learning	I can easily see where my friend's position is through the YukMaCa portal
10	The YukMaCa system does not help facilitate outdoor based learning	Access to locations on the visit is still difficult to achieve even though it has been assisted by route recommendation from the Android YukMaCa application

The results obtained from the usability test of student respondents are as shown in Figure 11 and the results of the teacher's post study in Figure 12, the value of user satisfaction can be translated qualitatively based on the acquisition of SUS scores, as shown in Figure 10 [22]

Figure 11 Representation of SUS Scale [22]

Figure 12 the result of usability testing YukMaCa sistem (students respondents)

Usability test results of respondents students get scores above 50 and less than 60 for statement 5 and statement 10 which means they are in a high marginal position, but still acceptable, this is related to some respondents not used to using digital map services and not yet understand how to read digital maps. While for other statements, the score is above 70 which means Acceptable. Overall obtained usability

score 74.64 so YukMaCa is acceptable category according to student respondents.

Figure 13 the result of usability testing YukMaCa sistem (teachers respondents)

For usability testing of teacher respondents obtained scores above 60 and less than 70 or in high marginal for statement 8 about setting avatars, questions and locations on the android application, some users are still hesitant to use these features on the android application, but for other statements are above 70 so the YukMaCa portal is in the acceptable category. Likewise, the overall score is 78.17, so YukMaCa is in the acceptable category according to teacher respondents.

5. Conclusion

Overall the average score of the ease testing results for YukMaCa android 6.25 (students and teachers), 6.52 for the average score of the results of testing the ease of YukMaCa website, the overall average score of the YukMaCa system ease level 6.39 (easy) so the YukMaCa system is easy to be used. Usability score for YukMaCa system is 74.67 (students) and 78.17 (teachers), the average overall usability score of YukMaCa system is 76.42 (Acceptable), therefore YukMaCa system can be accepted by students and teachers and the YukMaCa system can be used in outdoor classroom learning.

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